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D2.1 Conceptual model and best practices for high-quality metadata publishing

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Abstract

This deliverable describes a conceptual model for data quality assessment. Quality is perceived as a multi-dimensional, task-specific concept. We review quality dimensions that have been proposed in literature and define a flexible quality model. Our model is based on the usage of a variety of scoring functions applied to relevant indicators in order to create task-specific quality assessment metrics. Two concrete instantiations of the model are presented, for analyzing the quality of Linked Data and Linked Sensor Data on the Web. Best practices for high-quality data publishing on the Web are presented for both instantiations of our quality model.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Web of Linked Data has seen an exponential growth over the past five years. From 12 Linked Data sets catalogued in 2007, the Linked Data cloud has grown to almost 300 data sets encompassing approximately 31 billion triples, according to the most recent survey conducted in September 2011 (Deliverable 4.1).

The quality of the provided information varies as information providers have different levels of knowledge and different intentions. Therefore it is common that data may be incorrect or biased. Moreover, in order for data to be useful in Web-scale applications, there are a number of other facets that need to be considered. Is the data accessible and licensed for use? Where can the data be found? Can the data be interpreted by the tools that will be used to consume them? Is the data available for online Web-access so that applications can be connected to it on-the-fly?

Therefore, people and systems interested in consuming data from the Web are confronted with the increasingly difficult task of selecting high-quality information from the vast amount of Web-accessible information. We describe a conceptual model for assessing data quality that is based on the idea of quality as “fitness for use”. Instead of having the designer of an information system decide for the users on a single, fixed method to assess the quality of information, users are empowered to adapt a wide range of filtering policies according to their task-specific needs.

The conceptual model described builds on the literature in information quality in information systems, and is generic with respect to the application domain. Moreover, it is multi-faceted to account for the different aspects that may influence the fitness of a particular piece of information for task-specific usage. Our model does not classify data into good or bad. Instead, it attempts to qualify, for instance, how accessible, interpretable or consistent the data is. Thus, users can decide based on this multi-faceted qualification if such characteristics deem the data good enough for their intended use.

We present instantiations of this model with focus on Linked Data and Data Streams. We include the definition concrete assessment metrics for quality dimensions such as Accessibility, Interpretability, Understandability, Timeliness, Openness, Verifiability, Consistency, Completeness, Conciseness, Structuredness, Relevancy, Validity and Rating based.

Subsequently, we compile a set of best practices that emerged within the community of researchers and practitioners for publishing self-describing data on the Web, connecting these best practices to the quality model we describe. The best practices proposed can be used as a checklist by data providers in order to enhance the quality of information shared on the Web. The increase in quality that is obtained by adopting these best practices can be measured by the quality model presented in this deliverable. In collaboration with the EC-funded LOD2 Project, implementations of some of these metrics are in progress. In the future we plan to offer this quantification of quality back to the data set catalog at TheDataHub.org as a way to motivate data publishers to adopt best practices.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Web of Linked Data has seen an exponential growth over the past five years¹. From 12 Linked Data sets catalogued in 2007, the Linked Data cloud has grown to almost 300 data sets encompassing approximately 31 billion triples, according to the most recent survey [36], conducted in September 2011 (Deliverable 4.1 [46]).

The quality of the provided information varies as information providers have different levels of knowledge and different intentions. Therefore it is common that data may be incorrect or biased. Moreover, in order for data to be useful in Web-scale applications, there are a number of other facets that need to be considered. Is the data accessible and licensed for use? Where can the data be found? Can the data be interpreted by the tools that will be used to consume them? Is the data available for online Web-access so that applications can be connected to it on-the-fly?

Therefore, people and systems interested in consuming data from the Web are confronted with the increasingly difficult task of selecting high-quality information from the vast amount of Web-accessible information.

We describe a conceptual model for assessing data quality that is based on the idea of quality as “fitness for use” [37]. Instead of having the designer of an information system decide for the users on a single, fixed method to assess the quality of information, users are empowered to adapt a wide range of filtering policies according to their task-specific needs.

The conceptual model described builds on the literature in information quality in information systems [61, 59, 48, 22, 41], and is generic with respect to the application domain. Moreover, it is multi-faceted to account for the different aspects that may influence the fitness of a particular piece of information for task-specific usage. Our model does not classify data into good or bad. Instead, it attempts to qualify, for instance, how accessible, interpretable or consistent the data is. Thus, users can decide based on this multi-faceted qualification if such characteristics deem the data good enough for their intended use.

We present instantiations of this model with focus on Linked Data and Data Streams. We include the definition concrete assessment metrics for quality dimensions such as Accessibility, Interpretability, Understandability, Timeliness, Openness, Verifiability, Consistency, Completeness, Conciseness, Structuredness, Relevancy, Validity and Rating based.

In order to provide data providers with a checklist to enhance the quality of information shared on the Web, we include a set of best practices that emerged within the community of researchers and practitioners for publishing self-describing data on the Web. The checklist is in consonance with the quality model we describe, allowing the measurement of the increase in quality that is obtained by adopting these best practices. In collaboration with the EC-funded LOD2 Project, implementations of some of these metrics are in progress. In the future we plan to offer this quantification of quality back to the data set catalog at TheDataHub.org as a way to motivate data publishers to adopt best practices.

This report is organized as follows. Chapter 2 describes the conceptual model for data quality, and two concrete instantiations of this model: Section 2.1 describes quality assessment for Linked Data, and Section 2.2 describes quality assessment for data streams. Chapter 3 describes best practices for sharing self-describing data: Section 3.1 approaches the case of Linked Data, and Section 3.2 focuses on Linked Sensor Data.

¹<http://lod-cloud.net>

2 CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR DATA QUALITY

A popular definition for quality is “fitness for use” [37]. Most of the work in information quality has adopted this definition of quality as the fitness for use of information [61, 59, 48, 22, 41]. Therefore, the interpretation of the quality of some data item depends on who will use this information, and what is the task for which they intend to employ it. While one user may consider the data quality sufficient for a given task, it may not be sufficient for another task or another user.

Moreover, quality is commonly perceived as multifaceted, as the “fitness for use” may depend on several **dimensions** such as accuracy, timeliness, completeness, relevancy, objectivity, believability, understandability, consistency, conciseness, availability, and verifiability [9]. Table 2.1 [15] summarizes the most common quality dimensions from different catalogs presented in databases and information systems literature [14, 43, 27, 22, 61, 54, 34].

More specifically to the case of Linked Data, Hogan et al. [31] discuss an illustrative list of common errors in RDF publishing, detected from crawling 149,057 URIs containing RDF/XML. They identify four categories of symptoms: incomplete (when data cannot be retrieved), incoherent (when local data may be incorrectly interpreted), hijack (when remote data may be incorrectly interpreted) and inconsistent (when a contradiction may be interpreted from the data). Within these categories of symptoms, they describe quality problems and recommendations that fit within accessibility, interpretability, understandability, consistency, timeliness, and validity dimensions. Flemming and Hartig [24] also describe a catalog of quality criteria for Linked Data sources. They include approximately 60 indicators within the dimensions of consistency, timeliness, verifiability, uniformity, versatility, comprehensibility, validity of documents, amount of data, licensing, accessibility and performance.

In order to account for the multitude of quality dimensions that have been studied in the relevant literature, as well as to be flexible for evolving quality assessment needs, our conceptual model allows data consumers to describe which characteristics of the data indicate higher quality, and how this quality is quantified in a per-task basis. This is enabled by a conceptual model composed of indicators, scoring functions and assessment metrics [9].

A **Data Quality Indicator** is an aspect of a data item or data set that may give an indication to the user of the suitability of the data for some intended use. The types of information which may be used as quality indicators are very diverse. Besides the information to be assessed itself, indicators may stem from meta-information about the circumstances in which information was created, on background information about the information provider, or on ratings provided by the information consumers themselves, other information consumers, or domain experts.

A **Scoring Function** is an assessment of a data quality indicator to be evaluated by the user in the process of deciding on the suitability of the data for some intended use. There may be a choice of several scoring functions for producing a score based on a given indicator. Depending on the quality dimension to be assessed and the chosen quality indicators, scoring functions range from simple comparisons, like “assign true if the quality indicator has a value greater than X”, over set functions, like “assign true if the indicator is in the set Y”, aggregation functions, like “count or sum up all indicator values”, to more complex statistical functions, text-analysis, or network-analysis methods.

Assessment Metrics are procedures for measuring an information quality dimension. In our model, each assessment metric relies on a set of quality indicators and calculates an assessment score from these indicators using a scoring function. This model allows users to define several metrics for a given dimension. Depending on the task at hand, users may vary which indicators are taken as input, and which functions are using for quantifying the information quality, providing for more flexibility in quality assessment.

2.1 Quality Assessment for Linked Data Sets (LDS)

In this section we discuss an instantiation of our conceptual model for the case of Linked Data. We discuss a set of indicators, scoring functions, and assessment metrics that we consider to be important to move forward the current state of the Linked Data ecosystem.

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Count</i>
Accuracy	7
Timeliness	7
Completeness	6
Relevancy	5
Availability	5
Rep. Consistency	4
Amount of Data	4
Interpretability	3
Rep. Conciseness	3
Security	2
Objectivity	2
Believability	2
Understandability	2
Verifiability	2
Response Time	2
Consistency	2
Reputation	1

Table 2.1: Distribution of information quality dimensions [15].

2.1.1 Accessibility

The first step in data consumption is, naturally, to obtain access to some portion of data for use. The Accessibility category groups indicators and quality measures that describe one’s ability to get access to data.

Access methods. There are a number of ways to get access to data. Applications may prefer bulk access to a data set, while others may prefer the ability to select subsets through a query language. The *Access Methods* indicators $sparql(d)$, $bulk(d)$ and $sample(d)$ describe different characteristics for users to define what “accessible” means to them. Consider the following events:

- $sparql(d)$: “A SPARQL endpoint URL is provided for data set d .”
- $bulk(d)$: “URLs to files containing data set d in bulk are provided.”
- $sample(d)$: “An example resource is provided for data set d .”

For each of those events we can define indicator functions $1_{sparql(d)}$, $1_{bulk(d)}$, $1_{sample(d)}$ such that:

$$1_E(d) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d \notin E \\ 1 & \text{if } d \in E \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Where E is one of $\{sparql(d), bulk(d), sample(d)\}$. Taking as input these indicators, one can define an assessment metric *RDF Accessibility* that uses a weighted sum as a scoring function

$$RDF\ Accessibility = \alpha \times 1_{sparql(d)} + \beta \times 1_{bulk(d)} + \gamma \times 1_{sample(d)}$$

with weights $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, 1)$ allowing users to configure relative importance of each access method.

Reachability. One of the particularities of Linked Data is the interlinking between Web-accessible data items. Therefore, through such links, users or software agents are able to navigate between data items and “reach” other data sets much like Web crawlers do for Web pages. The indicator $external_links(d_1, d_2)$ formalizes this notion of a link between two datasets d_1 and d_2 , whenever there is a triple whose subject belongs to d_1 and

the object belongs to d_2 . Thus, we can measure how many datasets d_k link to a given dataset d with the indicator $indegree(d)$, which counts the number of triples that link between two sets in the universe of all known data sets D . Similarly, $outdegree(d)$ records the number of triples outgoing of one dataset.

- $external_links(d_1, d_2) = \{t(s, p, o) | s \in d_1 \wedge o \in d_2 \wedge d_1 \neq d_2\}$
- $indegree(d) = \sum_{d_k \in D} ||external_links(d_k, d)||$
- $outdegree(d) = \sum_{d_k \in D} ||external_links(d, d_k)||$

Therefore, an assessment metric of *LDS InDegree Reachability* can be used to measure the likelihood that a user or software agent browsing the LOD cloud will find a given dataset. In order to generate scores between 0 and 1, the $indegree(d)$ can be normalized by dividing the indegree of all data sets by a large constant – e.g. the number of triples in the cloud $\tau = \forall\{t | t(s, p, o) \in D\}$.

$$LDSInDegreeReachability = \frac{indegree(d)}{||\tau||}$$

Other assessment metrics could also be defined. For example, a *LDS PageRank Reachability* assessment metric could build on the intuition of the random surfer model, and generate scores through the PageRank algorithm [51]. The final PageRank for each data set $d \in D$ reflects the probability that a user or software agent would stop on this data set while randomly browsing the Web. Therefore, a higher *PageRank* score indicates that a data set is easier to reach from the Web of Data. The formula for computing the *PageRank* over a number of data sets - normalized to the (0,1) interval - is displayed in Equation 2.2.

$$PageRank(d_x) = \frac{1 - \delta}{||D||} + \delta \left(\frac{PageRank(d_y)}{L(d_y)} + \frac{PageRank(d_w)}{L(d_w)} + \frac{PageRank(d_z)}{L(d_z)} + \dots \right). \quad (2.2)$$

Where δ is a damping factor, and $L(d)$ is the set of links outgoing from dataset d .

$$L(d) = \frac{\sum_{d_k \in D} ||external_links(d, d_k)||}{||d||}$$

Therefore, we can define an assessment metric:

$$LDSPageRankReachability = PageRank(d)$$

Availability. Another important aspect of Linked Data is that data item descriptions are offered on the Web for online retrieval. That is, there is a service - e.g. a web server or a data-access application - which receives HTTP requests, acquires data and returns it in RDF format in an HTTP response. Therefore, for applications that make online usage of Linked Data, the availability of this service is a very important aspect. One can define availability as the percentage of time a given service is “up”, i.e. the service is able to provide a response when it receives a request. Therefore, we can define the events $http_get$ and $http_head$, and corresponding indicator functions 1_{http_head} and 1_{http_get} (analogous to Equation 2.1).

- $http_get(r)$: “the execution of an HTTP GET request to the URI r obtains a successful HTTP response”
- $sparql_query(r)$: “the execution of SPARQL Query via HTTP to the URI r obtains a successful HTTP response”
- $http_head(r)$: “the execution of an HTTP HEAD request to the URI r obtains a successful HTTP response”

We can then define the metrics $avail_sample$, $avail_sparql$ and $avail_bulk$ which score the indicators by their average availability in a time interval I .

- $avail_sample(d, I) : 1_{sample(d)} * \frac{\sum_{i \in I} http_get(sample(d))}{||I||}$
- $avail_sparql(d, I) : 1_{sparql(d)} * \frac{\sum_{i \in I} sparql_query(sparql(d))}{||I||}$
- $avail_bulk(d, I) : 1_{bulk(d)} * \frac{\sum_{i \in I} sparql_query(dump(d))}{||I||}$

Please recall the definition of aforementioned $sample(d)$, $sparql(d)$ and $bulk(d)$ and corresponding *Access Methods* indicator functions.

An assessment metric *LDSAvailability* can be defined by

$$LDSAvailability = \alpha \times avail_bulk(d) + \beta \times avail_sparql(d) + \gamma \times avail_sample(d)$$

with weights $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, 1)$ allowing users to configure relative importance of the availability for each access method. This metric can also be computed and averaged over time, displaying historical information that is more reliable than just considering the immediate state.

Response Time. Similarly to *Availability*, for many online applications it is important to consider how fast a service can respond with data, as this factor can deeply affect user experience in interacting with an online information system. The response time indicator measures the time in miliseconds that a service takes to respond with *http_get*, *http_head* and *sparql_query*.

- $time(E) =$ “time in miliseconds taken for the event E to complete”

Therefore, we define the scoring functions:

- $time_sparql(d) = time(sparql_query(dump(d)))$
- $time_sample(d) = time(http_get(sample(d)))$
- $time_bulk(d) = time(http_head(bulk(d)))$

An assessment metric *LDSResponseTime* can be defined by

$$LDSResponseTime = \alpha \times time_bulk(d) + \beta \times time_sparql(d) + \gamma \times time_sample(d)$$

with weights $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, 1)$ allowing users to configure relative importance of the response time for each access method. This metric can also be computed and averaged over time, displaying historical information that is more reliable than just considering the immediate state.

Robustness. In use cases where large chunks of data will be consumed over many requests, it is important to know beforehand what is the capacity of the provider. Some data providers will be able to respond to only a few requests per minute, while others will have limits on how much data they are able to serve in a given period of time. Therefore, the robustness of a dataset can be estimated by *the data provider itself* by running a self-stress test similar to the *Availability* metric, applied repeatedly in a short period of time.

Alternatively, third-parties can combine historical availability with the *Response Time*, in order to devise a robustness estimate. First, lower historical availability may indicate lower robustness, as the data provider is known to fail to respond to requests. Second, higher response time may indicate lower robustness. That is due to the assumption that during the time between request and response the service is busier, and therefore should be able to respond to a reduced number of requests.

2.1.2 Interpretability and Understandability

Understandability is the extent to which data is easily comprehended by the information consumer [53]. Understandability is related to interpretability. Interpretability refers to technical aspects, for instance, whether information is represented using an appropriate notation, while understandability refers to the subjective capability of the information consumer to comprehend information.

Format Interpretability. In order for applications to be able to integrate and effectively use data coming from disparate sources on the Web, it is first necessary to interpret the format in which this information is encoded. The W3C recommends RDF as the standard model for data exchange on the Web ¹. RDF can be serialized in several formats. The most common RDF serializations include RDF/XML, Turtle, N-Triples and NQuads. Therefore, we can define the following events:

- $rdf_xml(d)$: “The data set d can be parsed by a standard RDF/XML parser²”
- $turtle(d)$: “The data set d can be parsed by a standard Turtle parser²”
- $ntriples(d)$: “The data set d can be parsed by a standard N-Triples parser²”
- $nquads(d)$: “The data set d can be parsed by a standard NQuads parser²”

Similarly to Equation 2.1, indicator functions $1_{rdf_xml(d)}$, $1_{turtle(d)}$, $1_{ntriples(d)}$ and $1_{nquads(d)}$ can be defined for each of the aforementioned events.

An assessment metric $LDSFormatInterpretability$ can be defined by

$$LDSFormatInterpretability = \alpha \times 1_{rdf_xml(d)} + \beta \times 1_{turtle(d)} + \gamma \times 1_{ntriples(d)} + \epsilon 1_{nquads(d)}$$

with weights $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \epsilon \in (0, 1)$ allowing users to configure relative importance of each format. Under the assumption that more commonly used formats will make it more likely that a third-party application would be able to interpret your data, these weights can be automatically estimated by taking into consideration the amount of triples or data sets that use each format. Therefore, using the number of data sets $\|D\|$:

$$\alpha = \frac{\sum_{d \in D} 1_{rdf_xml(d)}}{\|D\|}$$

Human+Machine Interpretability. Since Linked Data sets are designed to ‘live’ on the Web amongst Web pages, it is recommended that they provide representations that can be interpreted both for humans and for machines. This is done for Linked Data URIs through the dereference mechanism [6]. For our purposes, a correctly dereferenced URI is one that, when used as the target address of an HTTP request, returns a response of the requested type. Content type can be requested by adding **Accept** headers to an HTTP request, while HTTP responses may describe the type of the returned content by including a **Content-type** header. Therefore, we extend the previously defined $http_get(r)$ to include also a requested type $http_get(r, f)$.

- $http_get(r, f)$: “the execution of an HTTP GET request to the URI r obtains a successful HTTP response where the format in the **Content-type** matches the format f in the **Accept** header.”

Let F_h be the set of formats that are tailored for human consumption of information on the Web, while F_m is the set of formats tailored for machine consumption. Naturally, these sets of formats can be extended, reduced or completely substituted according to task-specific needs.

- $F_h = \{HTML, XHTML+RDFa\}$
- $F_m = \{RDF/XML, NT, NQ, TTL\}$

Thus, we can define $deref_h(r) = \{http_get(r, f) | f \in F_h\}$ to indicate that a URI is dereferenceable to a human-readable format and, analogously, $deref_m(r)$ for machine-readable formats. An assessment metric $LDSHumanMachineInterpretability$ can then be defined as

$$LDSHumanMachineInterpretability = \sum_{r \in d} 1_{deref_h(r)} \times 1_{deref_m(r)}$$

This formulation of the assessment metric is quite strict – it generates 0 values if a resource does not dereference to *both* human and machine readable formats. Other formulations may use a weighted function to specify the individual importance of human and machine interpretability.

¹<http://www.w3.org/RDF/>

²For implementation purposes, the library Any23 (<http://code.google.com/p/any23/>) can be used as a standard parser.

Vocabulary Understandability. The effective use of a data set is constrained by how much of the underlying information can be understood by the human or software agent using it. One important step in understanding the data is successfully associating the vocabulary (or schema) of the data set with known concepts to the user. Therefore, a data set that uses schemata that are better known increases its chances of having its schema understood by agents consuming the data. There are other aspects of understandability that are out of the scope of this assessment metric, including understanding the structure, modelling choices, or the interplay between schema elements. For those cases, other metrics in the same dimension can be created, and potentially combined.

We realize the assessment of one *LDSVocabularyUnderstandability* assessment metric with the following rationale: if an agent understood part of the LOD cloud D , there is $X\%$ of chance it knows a given vocabulary v in the cloud. Therefore, we can estimate the likelihood that an agent will understand the vocabulary of a data set d if it's coming from the cloud by estimating how many triples use the vocabulary:

- $triples(v, d) = \{\forall t(s, p, o) \in d | v \in vocab(t)\}$
- $vocab(t(s, p, o)) = \{vocab(s) \cup vocab(p) \cup vocab(o)\}$
- $vocab(r) = \{v | r \in v\}$

Thus, we define

$$LDSVocabularyUnderstandability = triples(v, d) \times \frac{\sum_{d_k \in D} triples(v, d_k)}{||\tau||}$$

Alternatively, one could use the *PageRank* to estimate a probability that a random surfer has found the vocabulary v . Note that similar metrics can be applied to estimate the understandability of individual schema or instance URIs.

Internationalization Understandability. As URIs are intended to uniquely identify concepts in a global data space, RDF provides mechanisms for “language localization”. For example, data providers are encouraged to provide `rdfs:label` properties with several language tags such as `@en` (for English), `@pt` for Portuguese, etc. An assessment metric for *Internationalization Understandability* can measure, for example, what portion of a data set has labels for a given target language. Besides `rdfs:label`, other properties such as `skos:preferredLabel` and `skos:altLabel` can also be used for providing labels, and defining an acceptable set of properties is a task-specific decision. Therefore, we can define the following events:

- $label(r, l)$: “the resource r contains a label in language l .”

Thus, we define:

$$LDSi18nUnderstandability(d, l) = \frac{\sum_{t \in d} 1_{label(r, l)}}{||d||}$$

2.1.3 Timeliness

Timeliness is the degree to which information is up-to-date [38]. Timeliness can be seen as an intrinsic dimension, meaning that information represents the current state of the real world [48]. Timeliness can also be seen as contextual, meaning that the information is timely enough to be used for a specific task [53]. We define two assessment metrics that are related to the timeliness dimension.

Newness measures if data has been created in a timely manner. For tasks comparing historical information, knowing when a certain piece of information was created is as important as the information itself. An indicator that can be used for newness is the Dublin Core metadata term `dc:created` [32]. Selecting the best indicator for computing newness depends on the existence and usage of standards in the application domain.

Freshness measures if some data has been updated in a timely manner. For some tasks, data can get stale and lose its value, therefore highlighting the need for analyzing the freshness of information. Indicators that can be used for freshness include the HTTP header `Last-Modified` [28] and Dublin Core metadata

term `dc:modified` [32]. Similarly to newness and other metrics, the selection of indicators is a task-dependent activity.

Let:

- $seconds(date_1, date_2)$ = “number of seconds spent since $date_1$ until $date_2$ ”
- $created(d)$ = “date of creation of d according to an indicator chosen by the user”
- $modified(d)$ = “date of modification of d according to an indicator chosen by the user”
- $today$ = “today’s date”

In the contextual interpretation of timeliness, both metrics can be implemented by scoring the indicators by how far they are from the ideal freshness or newness necessary for a given task. Therefore, if $timespan$ represents the ideal freshness or newness in seconds informed by the user as a parameter, we can define the $LDSNewness$ and the $LDSFreshness$ of a dataset d as:

$$LDSNewness(d, timespan) = time_distance(timespan, created(d))$$

$$LDSFreshness(d, timespan) = time_distance(timespan, modified(d))$$

Where:

$$time_distance(timespan, date) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } seconds(date, today) > timespan \\ 1 - \frac{seconds(date, today)}{timespan} & \text{if } seconds(date, today) \leq timespan \end{cases}$$

2.1.4 Openness

According to the Open Knowledge Foundation (OKFN): “A piece of content or data is open if anyone is free to use, reuse, and redistribute it – subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and share-alike.”

The OKFN maintains a list of Conformant Licenses³. One possible *Openness* assessment metric can be implemented by checking if the license provided with the data set belongs to the list of OKFN Conformant Licenses. As of Feb 15th this list includes: Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence (PDDL), Open Data Commons Attribution License, Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL), Creative Commons CCZero. This list can be extended or reduced according to the use case, for example, to include country-specific licenses – common within government data sets.

2.1.5 Verifiability

Verifiability is the degree and ease with which the information can be checked for correctness [48]. Related concepts are traceability, provability and accountability. For information which might be biased, verifiability plays an important role in the information consumer’s decision whether to accept information [48].

Traceability is the ability to follow the history of an item, including other items and processes used in its creation or delivery. The W3C Provenance Working Group⁴ aims at supporting the widespread publication of such information by means of a standard model. Traceability assessment metrics can be built based on indicators drawn from this model. For example, a minimalistic take on traceability would be to require that every dataset describes its author – e.g. using the Dublin Core metadata term `dc:creator` [32]. The kinds and depth of required provenance information for each task will define which indicators to use.

Accountability can be defined as the responsibility to someone for a given piece of information. It indicates the willingness or obligation to account for this piece of information. Since one of the driving principles of the Web of Data is that anybody can describe any piece of information, it is very common that open data sets are reformatted and republished as Linked Data. However, the original data set may contain errors, or inaccuracies

³<http://opendefinition.org/licenses/>

⁴<http://www.w3.org/2011/prov>

may be introduced in the reformatting process. For this reason, it is important to distinguish between publisher and producer of data sets. The data sets catalogue metadata schema used in the Planet Data Sets Catalogue (D4.1) [46] includes such descriptors, namely: **published-by-producer** and **published-by-third-party**. One possible interpretation is that data sets published by the producer have higher accountability.

2.1.6 Consistency

Consistency implies that two or more values do not conflict with each other [43]. Information on the Web is likely to be inconsistent as it is provided by multiple information providers, which might use different procedures to capture information, have different levels of knowledge and different views of the world.

One way to measure the **consistency** of a data set is by considering properties with cardinality 1 that contain more than one (distinct) value. We have defined the *consistency* of a data set for a given property p to measure the proportion of objects that do not contain more than one **distinct** value for p , with regard to the universe of unique property values.

$$Consistency(p) = \frac{||obj. without conflicts for p in data set||}{||all uniq. obj. with p in dataset||} \quad (2.3)$$

2.1.7 Completeness

Naturally, the completeness of a data set can only be judged in the presence of a task where the (size of the) ideal set of attributes and objects are known.

Intensional Completeness On the schema level, a data set is complete if it contains all of the attributes needed for a given task [10].

$$Intensional Completeness = \frac{||uniq. attr. in data set||}{||all uniq. attr. in universe||} \quad (2.4)$$

Extensional Completeness On the data (instance) level, a data set is complete if it contains all of the necessary objects for a given task [10].

$$Extensional Completeness = \frac{||uniq. obj. in data set||}{||all uniq. obj. in universe||} \quad (2.5)$$

LDS Completeness Another, more fine grained, way to compute completeness is by taking into consideration the instantiations of properties (number of triples using each property). That is, it measures the proportion of objects that contain a value for a given property p , in relation to the universe of objects that contain that property (Equation 2.6).

$$Completeness(p) = \frac{||obj. with property p in data set||}{||all uniq. obj. in universe||} \quad (2.6)$$

See Mendes, Mühleisen and Bizer [45] for an example of this metric in use.

2.1.8 Conciseness

Conciseness regards the uniqueness of objects or object descriptions in a data set. Conciseness can be increased by removing redundant data, by fusing duplicate entries and merging common attributes into one.

Intensional Conciseness On the schema level, a data set is concise if it does not contain redundant attributes (two equivalent attributes with different names). The *intensional conciseness* measures the number of unique attributes of a dataset in relation to the overall number of attributes in a target schema [10].

Extensional Conciseness On the data (instance) level, a data set is concise if it does not contain redundant objects (two equivalent objects with different identifiers). The *extensional conciseness* measures the number of unique objects in relation to the overall number of object representations in the data set [10].

LDS Conciseness Similarly to completeness, we can define a finer grained *conciseness* metric for a given property p to measure the proportion of objects that do not contain more than one **identical** value for p (redundant), with regard to the universe of unique property values (Equation 2.7).

$$\text{Conciseness}(p) = \frac{||\text{obj. with uniq. values for } p \text{ in data set}||}{||\text{all uniq. obj. with } p \text{ in dataset}||} \quad (2.7)$$

Representational Conciseness. The representational conciseness measures the extent to which information is compactly represented [53]. The most common representation formats for Linked Data have focused on encoding information in a self-descriptive and unambiguous manner, and have not been particularly concerned with being concise. However, for exchanging high volumes of data, as it is the case of streaming data, representational conciseness is a very important dimension. One RDF format that focuses on encoding RDF in a highly compressed representation is RDF HDT ⁵.

An assessment metric to evaluate this aspect for Linked Data can be defined as how many triples can be encoded per kilobyte:

$$\text{LDSRepresentationalConciseness} = \frac{||d||}{\text{filesize}}$$

2.1.9 Structuredness

As some applications may heavily rely on structured data – e.g. for complex query execution – it is important to know how structured a given data set is, in order to judge if the dataset is fit for a given task. Duan et al. [21] proposed *Coverage* and *Coherence* metrics for measuring the structuredness of a data set. They determine the level of structuredness of a data set d with respect to a schema v by how well the instance data in d conform to the schema v [21]. Suppose that a schema v has properties a , b , and c . If almost every instance has property values for a , b , and c , then they have a similar structure that conforms with v . Therefore, this data set has high structuredness with regard to v .

The *Coverage* of a class c within a data set d is computed by the formula shown in Equation 2.10.

$$\text{Coverage}(c, d) = \frac{\sum_{\forall p \in P(c)} OC(p, I(c, d))}{|P(c)| \times |I(c, d)|} \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

- $P(c)$: set of properties that belong to class c
- $OC(p, d)$: number of occurrences of property p within triples in d .
- $I(c, d)$: set of instances of class c in data set d .

It is possible that a data set has a low structuredness for a class c_1 , but high structuredness for a class c_2 . In order to measure the structuredness of a data set, the coverage of each class c can be weighted by how many properties and instances belong to c , as shown in equation (Equation 2.9).

$$\text{WT}(\text{Coverage}(c, d)) = \frac{|P(c)| + |I(c, d)|}{\sum_{\forall c' \in V} (|P(c')| + |I(c', d)|)} \quad (2.9)$$

Then, the *Coherence* of a dataset is measured by:

$$\text{Coherence}(V, d) = \sum_{\forall c \in v; \forall v \in V} \text{WT}(\text{Coverage}(c, d)) \times \text{Coverage}(c, d) \quad (2.10)$$

⁵<http://www.w3.org/Submission/2011/SUBM-HDT-20110330/>

2.1.10 Relevancy

Relevancy is the extent to which information is applicable and helpful for the task at hand [53]. Relevancy is an important quality dimension in the context of web-based systems, as information consumers are often confronted with an overflow of potentially relevant information. Relevancy is perhaps one of the most task-specific and subjective quality dimensions. Ways to measure relevance depend on the user, task, domain of knowledge, data representation, etc.

Within search engines, for example, approaches to assess the relevancy of web documents sort documents according to their relevancy for a given query using a combination of hyperlink analysis [51] and information retrieval methods [23].

Similar approaches can also be used for Linked Data. For instance, Nikolov et al. [49] propose ways to find relevant data sets through a semantic Web index. Their task is to find data sets that are relevant for interlinking. The data model of interest was RDF. Therefore, based on this task-specific information, the relevancy in their case was defined in terms of the number of overlapping terms between the source and candidate target data sets, amount of additional information such as properties, as well as the popularity of the target data set.

2.1.11 Validity

Validity is a very generic notion that refers to the set of assumptions or requirements regarding the data that are made by the applications that are using the data. For example, for the purposes of query optimization it has been argued that assuming acyclic class and property hierarchies significantly improves the algorithms' performance [57]. Other applications may require the introduction of cardinality constraints, functional properties or other context-specific constraints (such as e.g., the requirement that a person cannot be his own father).

These kinds of constraints can be expressed using some expressive rule-based formalism. In PlanetData, we employ Disjunctive Embedded Dependencies (DEDs) [20], which are expressive enough to capture a variety of integrity constraints related to frequently-used invalidities of RDF(S) datasets such as acyclicity of certain properties (e.g., subsumption) [57], cardinality constraints [47] and others.

Validity is a crucial requirement because data that does not satisfy the application-imposed requirements could cause the related applications to function sub-optimally, or fail altogether, i.e., rendering the data useless. This is in contrast with some of the other quality metrics, e.g., timeliness, which are important but cannot cause applications to fail or render data useless for a particular purpose. Due to the importance of validity as a quality metric, it is studied in more detail in Deliverable D2.2⁶, where we also consider techniques for imposing validity, i.e., repair approaches that modify invalid datasets in order to render them valid, causing minimal changes on the original data (according to some custom, user-defined metric of minimality).

2.1.12 Reputation

The *Reputation* dimension captures the beliefs or opinions that users may explicitly or implicitly attribute to data. For example, the *PageRank* [51] technique (shown in Equation 2.2) has been used to estimate the reputation of Web sites based on the link structure of the Web. Pages that have many incoming links are considered more important. Similarly, *PageRank* can be used to estimate the reputation of a data set based on how many other data sets have linked to it.

Reputation can also be measured through explicit ratings about the data, data sources, or data providers. Explicit ratings can be observed when users attribute 'thumbs up' or '5 star' ratings to data or people. This dimension is orthogonal to the others, as ratings can be used to aggregate opinions on any of the other dimensions, or as an overall subjective assessment of a data sets quality given by a consumer, provider or expert.

The Linked Data vision of the Web as a global data space [29], any data consumer, data provider or third party can express their opinion about any data sets or data items on the Web. Revyu and Schema.org are two examples of ways to encode opinions about resources on the Web. Some portals, such as the data catalog TheDataHub.org and its underlying software (CKAN), support the rating of data sets by users browsing their catalogs.

⁶<http://planet-data-wiki.sti2.at/web/D2.2>

Any collection of such explicit ratings can be used as indicators, and through weighted functions they may be combined into a *LDSRating* assessment metric. Moreover, implicit ratings may also be combined, for example by the usage of *PageRank*.

2.2 Quality Assessment for Sensors and Streaming Data

As technologies in sensing and wireless communication continue to proliferate, huge volumes of sensor data are being collected and used in a variety of applications. One typical characteristic of such data is in uncertain and erroneous nature, originating from various sources, such as discharged batteries, network failures, and imprecise readings from low-cost sensors [35, 62, 26]. This poses a significant problem on data utilization, since applications using erroneous data may yield unsound results. For example, a wide range of scientific applications perform prediction tasks using observation data obtained from cheap but less-reliable sensors, which may render the prediction results incorrect due to the presence of errors or inaccurate values in the data.

To address this problem, it is essential to compute the quality of data, and perform data processing while reflecting the data quality. To this end, we focus on some important dimensions for dealing with the quality of sensor data, among those already defined in the previous section. In this section, we describe the quality dimensions considered for representing sensor data quality, as well as the method to compute some of the dimensions. We then present a data-cleaning system that cleans sensor data based to the quality assessed by our method.

Figure 2.1: Functional components of a typical sensor device

2.2.1 Quality Indicators for Sensor Devices

Sensor nodes typically contain four main functional components : a central processing unit and memory, a communication module, a power module and a sensor/actuator module (see Figure 2.1). The main limitations of these devices come from the power module, the communication module and the CPU and memory module. The power module can be implemented using one or a combination of the following: external power (mains), battery power or some form of energy harvesting (e.g. solar, wind, vibration). The latter two options lead to sensor nodes with limited lifetime and operation modes that include a sleeping mechanism. The communication module can be implemented using wired or wireless technology. In both cases, it is typically optimized to consume as little power as possible, therefore the transmission range is limited, and as little memory for the code as possible therefore making difficult to run full HTTP/TCP/IP protocol stack. Furthermore, in the case of the wireless implementation, due to the characteristics of the wireless channels, the communication is unreliable and the topology dynamic. The CPU and memory module's technical specifications vary a lot from 8 bit to 32 bit CPU, from 16 KB to up to 1 MB of memory. These limit the processing speed, as well as the size of the application code and data.

All these characteristics of sensor nodes can influence sensor data quality in terms of:

- Completeness and availability dimensions, as the limited lifetime or operation mode could cause missing values in the stream of measurements.
- Accuracy dimension, considering the risk of receiving corrupted data, due to communication failures.

- Interpretability and understandability dimensions; the CPU and memory limitations affects the level to which raw sensor measurements can be processed on the sensor node, before it is further sent to a central server.

Therefore it is important to specify the sensor nodes characteristics (metadata) in a machine readable form, which would help in further analysis of sensor data quality.

The sensor metadata can be stored, represented and (web) accessed in several ways.

- It can be stored in large repositories such as enterprise servers and databases which are part of the middleware or they can reside on the sensor nodes themselves.
- The metadata can be represented via a custom approach which is system specific or a standardized approach which allows compatibility among systems.
- Web access to the metadata can be provided from central servers or from sensor nodes (capable of connecting to the web).

Independent of the methods used for storing, representing and accessing the metadata, the following general guidelines should be considered when dealing with metadata:

- flexibility: it should allow the description of any sensor node and it should be easy to adapt to new requirements
- ease of embedding: it should be simple to add metadata
- ease of retrieval: it should be easy to access metadata
- maintainability: when the software for the sensors has to be changed, the corresponding metadata should be easy to adapt to the changes

Providing support for describing sensor nodes metadata, gives the possibility to add also technical specifications of sensors. For instance, the SunSpot v0.6 device features several sensors, among others, also a light sensor. By consulting the documentation, we can see that we are dealing with an Avago ADJD-S311-CR999 RGB digital color sensor with a 10-bit analog to digital converter, that it returns an integer between 0 to 750 where 0 stands for complete darkness and the rule of how the luminance maps to raw reading: 1000 lx correspond to a reading of 497, 100 lx to 50 and 10 lx to 5. From the service composition point of view, the type of the sensor (also the product code), the feature of interest, the range of the output, the mapping curve and the error/tolerance may be of interest: <digital, light, <0, 750>, «1000 lx, 497>, <100 lx, 50>, <10lx, 5>, 0.1%>. All of these metadata can be used as indicators for quality assessment metrics in the dimensions: availability, response time, robustness, accuracy, etc.

From the representation point of view, the metadata can be represented via a custom approach which is system specific or a standardized approach which allows compatibility among systems. Among the standardized representations, several solutions exist; typically these depend on which community was involved in their development and how much emphasis was put to expressiveness and interoperability.

Solutions with high expressiveness and good interoperability characteristics are typically based on XML syntax: SensorML, ZigBee SmartEnergy and RDF. More recent, JSON is a popular, lower overhead alternative to XML. Solutions typically use a publicly shared schema, vocabulary or ontology to annotate data. For instance, what we call throughout this paper a sensor would be annotated as `Sensor` according to both SensorML and SSN ontology. More specifically, it can be annotated as `SensingDevice` according to Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology as we mostly refer to physical device rather than abstract (virtual) ones. However, what we call `sensor node` or `device` would be annotated as `System`. The SSN ontology is the result of a standardization effort lead by a W3C working group which consolidated the numerous sensor network ontologies developed in the recent years. The SSN ontology is able to provide the core concepts and relations needed for describing sensor metadata, therefore it is an infrastructure specific ontology. However, in most usage scenarios, additional ontologies are needed, depending on the domain of application. Typically the use of ontologies in sensor networks can be classified into four layers (Gray, et al., 2011):

- upper layer, comprised of upper-level ontologies used for the interoperability with other ontologies.
- infrastructure layer, describing the information required for the infrastructure (i.e., sensor network deployment, services provided by the infrastructure, metadata about sensor streams.)
- external layer, representing concepts which are not directly related to the sensor domain, such as geographical information.
- domain layer, defining the domain concepts related to a specific scenario where the sensor networks are used (e.g., floods, landslides, oil spills, etc).

For efficient storage or transmission of metadata, some implementations may use encoding techniques which perform compression. For XML syntax Efficient XML Interchange (EXI), Binary XML (BXML) and Fast Infoset have been considered in the literature (Shelby, 2010) while for JSON the emerging approach is Binary JSON (BSON), for RDF, there is RDF-HDT⁷.

2.2.2 Accuracy Dimension

Similarly to the other cases already discussed, the quality of sensor data is also multi-fold. We believe that the following quality dimensions are particularly important: *Accuracy*, *Timeliness*, *Response time*, *Availability*, *Robustness*, *Representational Conciseness*, *Objectivity*, and *Reputation*. Some of these are in fact straightforward to compute; others are very difficult to precisely infer.

We give here some references from the literature, where these dimensions have been considered for quality assessment, with relation to sensor data:

- **Accuracy** [5], [55], [60], [30]. Our approach is to the closest to [55].
- **Confidence** [40], [39].
- **Volatility** [5], [12].
- **Consistency** [5], [30].
- **Data Volume** [40], it is called amount of data in [39]
- **Granularity** [39],
- **Completeness** [55], [40], [39], [30].
- **Timeliness** [5], [60], [40], [39], [30].

Accuracy is certainly one of the most important dimensions in quality-aware sensor data management, so we shall focus on this dimension in the remaining of this section. At the same time, it is very difficult to compute the accuracy of a given sensor reading, since true values corresponding to the given (inaccurate) data values are generally unobservable. To tackle this problem, LSIR-EPFL has developed an accurate method to infer the accuracy of sensor data readings. We briefly describe the method in the sequel.

Figure 2.2 shows two sensor data obtained from a real sensor network deployment monitoring ambient temperature and humidity. The regions shown as Region A in Figure 2.2(a) and Figure 2.2(b) exhibit higher volatilities than those marked as Region B in the figures. This observation strongly suggests that the quality assessment of sensor data should be strongly related to this time-varying variance.

To reflect this idea, we first infer time-dependant (Gaussian) probability distributions. We then detect the values (anomalies) that reside out of three standard deviations (3σ) in the inferred distributions. This is because most values (approximately a 99.7% of given data values) are statistically expected to be within the 3σ bounds in the inferred probability densities. In the following paragraphs we introduce the GARCH model that can accurately model the time-varying error tolerance.

⁷<http://www.w3.org/Submission/2011/SUBM-HDT-20110330/>

Figure 2.2: Regions of changing volatility in (a) ambient temperature and (b) relative humidity.

More specifically, we assume that a raw data value v_t at time t contains some white noise a_t , which is modeled as $v_t = v'_t + a_t$, where v'_t denotes an unobservable true value. Given a (sliding) window $w = \langle v_{t-|w|-1}, v_{t-|w|}, \dots, v_{t-1} \rangle$ having $|w|$ values, we then infer v'_t and a_t using the ARMA (AutoRegressive Moving Average) model [58]. Formally,

$$v'_t = \phi_o + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_j v_{t-j} - \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j a_{t-j}$$

where ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_p are autoregressive coefficients, $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_q$ are moving average coefficients, ϕ_o is a constant, (p, q) are non-negative integers denoting the model order, and a_t obeys a zero mean normal distribution with variance σ_a^2 .

During the above process, we obtain the conditional variances a_t . We use these a_t to estimate volatilities of the time series using the GARCH (Generalized AutoRegressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity) model [11]. The GARCH model computes time-varying volatilities using a_t and infers Gaussian densities. Formally, the conditional variance σ_t^2 is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_t^2 &= \mathbb{E}((v_t - v'_t)^2 | F_{t-1}), \\ &= \mathbb{E}(a_t^2 | F_{t-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where $\mathbb{E}(a_t^2 | F_{t-1})$ is the variance of a_t , derived from given all the information F_{t-1} available until time $t - 1$.

The GARCH model describes the behavior of time-varying variance σ_t^2 as specified by 2.11. Specifically, a GARCH(m, s) model models volatility as a linear function of a_t^2 's as:

$$a_t = \sigma_t \epsilon_t, \quad \sigma_t^2 = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha_j a_{t-j}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^s \beta_j \sigma_{t-j}^2$$

where ϵ_t is a sequence of independent and identically distributed (*i.i.d.*) random variables, (m, s) are parameters describing the model order, $\alpha_0 > 0$, $\alpha_j \geq 0$, $\beta_j \geq 0$, and $\sum_{j=1}^{\max(m, s)} (\alpha_j + \beta_j) < 1$. The underlying idea of the GARCH(m, s) model is to reflect the fact that large shocks (a_i) tend to be followed by other large shocks. In many practical applications the GARCH model is typically used as the GARCH(1,1) model, since for a higher order GARCH model specifying the model order is a difficult task [58]. Thus, we also follow these model order settings. More details regarding estimation of model parameters and choosing sliding window size $|w|$ are described in [58].

The framework we have outlined above enables to speak about **accuracy** of sensor data. Although we did not express the accuracy in a closed formula, as we did in Section 2.1 for LOD quality dimensions, if we assume a given model (with predefined parameters, if our model is parameterized), we can indeed characterize numerically the accuracy dimension of sensor data quality w.r.t. this model.

Next, we specify bounds indicating three standard deviations in the inferred densities, in order to represent the data space where the value at time t is highly likely to appear (i.e., a 99.7% chance). We then report any value that does not reside within the bounds as an anomaly.

2.2.3 The Data Cleaning System

To apply our method to measure the quality of sensor data, we have built a prototype system that performs data cleaning based on the quality computed. This subsection offers descriptions of the system, as well as presents a scenario of how the system works while interacting with users. This cleaning method could be also considered as a repair mechanism. Other quality repair techniques (especially for linked data) are discussed in deliverable D2.2 [25]. As the detection and elimination of accuracy problems in sensor data are closely related to each other, we discuss our techniques below.

System Overview

Figure 2.3 illustrates the architecture of the data cleaning system, consisting of four major components: *user interface*, *stream processing engine (GSN)*, *anomaly detector*, and *data storage*. In the following, we describe the details for each component.

Figure 2.3: Architecture of the data cleaning system.

User Interface.

The system provides a user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI) that plays two roles in the system. First, it takes all necessary inputs from users to perform data cleaning, which are a sensor data stream to be processed, a model with its parameters for anomaly detection, and an online/offline processing mode. Second, the outliers captured by our anomaly detector are presented using graphs and tables through the GUI, so that users can confirm whether each outlier is an actual error. The confirmed results are then stored to (or removed from) the underlying data storage as materialized views.

Stream Processing Engine (GSN).

We maintain streaming sensor data with *Global Sensor Network (GSN)*⁸ [1] that supports flexible integration of sensor networks and sensor data, provides distributed querying and filtering, and offers dynamic adaptation of the system configuration during operation. In our system, GSN receives and manages the sensor data streaming

⁸<http://gsn.sourceforge.net/>

from a number of heterogeneous sensors in different sensor-network deployments. It also serves as the main platform, where the other system components can cooperatively perform the data cleaning.

Anomaly Detector.

This component implements the parametric and the nonparametric diagnostics described in the previous section. The results from this anomaly detector are then presented through the user interface. Since the implementation of this component is embedded into GSN, the anomaly detector can work in online as well as offline fashions. In the online mode, whenever a new data value is streamed to GSN, the value is investigated whether it is dirty, and then errors are filtered out instantly. Moreover, the information about these errors are also recorded in our sensor metadata repository that will be described in the next section.

Data Storage.

This component maintains not only raw sensor data but also corresponding error-pruned data as materialized views. This is because applications on sensor networks often need to reprocess the data cleaning over the same data using different parameter settings for the models, when the previous parameter settings turn out to be inappropriate later. Therefore, it is important for the system to store cleaned data in database views without changing the original data, so that data cleaning can be performed again at any point of time (interval) whenever necessary. In addition, this data storage is flexible to be built upon various underlying database management systems that GSN supports, such as Oracle, MySQL, and PostgreSQL.

Processing Scenario

In order to better describe the procedure of the data cleaning process, we offer a working scenario of our system in this section.

Setting Target Data and Model.

Users specify some inputs for data cleaning through our GUI (Figure 2.4). These inputs include data source information for the data cleaning, such as (i) *Deployment* where sets of (heterogeneous) sensors are distributed on field sites, (ii) *Sensor* that indicates a particular sensor data stream in the deployment chosen, and (iii) *From* and *To* that specify a time interval for the selected stream to which the data-cleaning process applies.

The inputs also cover model settings; (iv) *Model* that is used for true value inference, (v) *Error bound* that sets a threshold for finding outliers when the difference between model-inferred true value and its corresponding raw value exceeds the error bound, and (vi) *Window*⁹ size that specifies the number of (consecutive) raw values to be used for the model construction. When the users select “GARCH” for the model type selection, the anomaly detection switches to the nonparametric diagnostics mode. This renders the settings for the error bound and the window size unnecessary because the system sets these in an automated manner, thus the corresponding selection boxes in the GUI become inactive.

Anomaly Visualization.

When the users press the *Apply model* button in the GUI (under the model parameter setting section in Figure 2.4), the system executes either of the diagnostics in our anomaly detector. The anomalies detected by the diagnostics are then visualized using various graphical tools, which could greatly improve the users’ understanding of the data. In Figure 2.4 and Figure 2.5, for example, raw data streams are plotted as green curves, while corresponding model-inferred values are overlaid by black curves. The anomaly points are then indicated by underlying red histograms as well as red circles (Figure 2.5). This allows users to easily identify errors from the anomalies detected while comparing the original data with the model-processed data. Our GUI also permits users to zoom in/out the graphs for effective anomaly identification. The small window at the left-bottom of Figure 2.4 shows the full range of the data space (i.e. time interval) where the users specified for data cleaning; while the main window containing the large graphs covers only a subspace of the full range of the data.

Erroneous Value Selection.

In addition to the graph plotting, the GUI provides a text representation for the anomalies, shown as the list boxes at right sides of Figure 2.4 and Figure 2.5. This is performed by clicking the button of the *Get dirty data*

⁹We use both terms ‘window’ and ‘segment’ interchangeably in this paper.

Figure 2.4: A snapshot of model-based data cleaning, using constant regressions.

button in Figure 2.4. Each item shown, i.e. anomaly, in the list boxes consists of a triple of (id, value, difference between the raw value and its corresponding model-driven true value). When the users select (or deselect) any item in the lists by clicking, a red circle appears (or disappears) over the corresponding raw data point in the graphs. We also provide a threshold-based selection that selects all items whose differences are greater than the threshold typed (the text boxes under the list boxes). By doing this, the users would be able to verify whether the detected data points are realistic (by visual observation), confirming them as erroneous data points.

Replayable Cleaning.

When the error selection in the previous step is completed, the users may press the **Delete dirty data** button in the GUI (Figure 2.4). The data cleaning system then removes all erroneous points selected, and stores only cleaned data to the data storage as a materialized view. The cleaned data is then displayed through the GUI, excluding the 'dirty' data points. Furthermore, the information for the dirty values is stored as metadata in another system component, so that the users can refer to or analyze the errors at any later time.

Note that our system also keeps the raw data regardless of the data cleaning. This permits the users to replay the data cleaning over the same data using different models or parameter settings, in case the previous data cleaning turns out to be inappropriate later.

Figure 2.5: Detected anomalies based on 2-degree Chebyshev regressions.

3 BEST PRACTICES FOR SHARING SELF-DESCRIBING DATA

According to the W3C Technical Architecture Group (TAG), in order to support flexible exploration by humans and agents, data on the Web should be as self-descriptive as possible [44]. The following two subsections provide concrete guidelines on how such self-descriptiveness is realized for different scenarios: Linked Data (Section 3.1) and Sensor Data (Section 3.2).

3.1 Linked Data Publishing Recommendations

A number of best practices have emerged in the Linked Data community, composing a set of recommendations for higher quality data publishing on the Web. In addition to providing your data via dereferenceable HTTP URIs, your data set should also ensure that data is as self-descriptive as possible, thereby enabling client applications to discover all relevant meta-information required to integrate data from different sources. The Linked Data Publishing Checklist [29] included below can be used by Linked Data publishers to verify that data meets the key requirements.

3.1.1 Does your data provide links to other data sets?

RDF links connect data from different sources into a single global RDF graph and enable Linked Data browsers and crawlers to navigate between data sources. Thus your data set should set RDF links pointing at other data sources [7].

3.1.2 Do you provide provenance metadata?

In order to enable applications to be sure about the origin of data as well as to enable them to assess the quality of data, data sources should publish provenance meta data together with the primary data. The metadata should include, for instance, information about authorship of a data set and its recency (i.e., when it was last updated). Recommendations on how to represent lineage information are presented in the final report from the W3C Provenance Working Group ¹.

3.1.3 Do you provide licensing metadata?

Web data should be self-descriptive concerning any restrictions that apply to its usage. All Linked Data published on the Web should include explicit *license* or *waiver* statements [52]. A common way to express such restrictions is to attach a data license to published data. Doing so is essential to enable applications to use Web data on a secure legal basis.

3.1.4 Do you use terms from widely deployed vocabularies?

In order to make it easier for applications to understand Linked Data, data providers should use terms from widely deployed vocabularies to represent data wherever possible. Reuse of existing terms is highly desirable as it increases the chances that third-parties will be able to understand your data. A few examples of well known vocabularies are [29]:

- The **Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) Metadata Terms** vocabulary (<http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms/>) defines general metadata attributes such as *title*, *creator*, *date* and *subject*.
- The **Friend-of-a-Friend (FOAF)** vocabulary (<http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>) defines terms for describing persons, their activities and their relations to other people and objects.

¹<http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/prov/XGR-prov-20101214/>

- The **Semantically-Interlinked Online Communities (SIOC)** vocabulary (<http://rdfs.org/sioc/spec/>) (pronounced "*shock*") is designed for describing aspects of online community sites, such as users, posts and forums.
- The **Description of a Project (DOAP)** vocabulary (<http://trac.usefulinc.com/doap>) (pronounced "*dope*") defines terms for describing software projects, particularly those that are Open Source.
- The **Music Ontology** (<http://musicontology.com/>) defines terms for describing various aspects related to music, such as artists, albums, tracks, performances and arrangements.
- The **Programmes Ontology** (<http://www.bbc.co.uk/ontologies/programmes/2009-09-07.shtml>) defines terms for describing programmes such as TV and radio broadcasts.
- The **Good Relations Ontology** (<http://purl.org/goodrelations/>) defines terms for describing products, services and other aspects relevant to e-commerce applications.
- The **Creative Commons (CC)** schema (<http://creativecommons.org/ns#>) defines terms for describing copyright licenses in RDF.
- The **Bibliographic Ontology (BIBO)** (<http://bibliontology.com/>) provides concepts and properties for describing citations and bibliographic references (i.e., quotes, books, articles, etc.).
- The **OAI Object Reuse and Exchange** vocabulary (<http://www.openarchives.org/ore/>) is used by various library and publication data sources to represent resource aggregations such as different editions of a document or its internal structure.
- The **Review Vocabulary** (<http://purl.org/stuff/rev#>) provides a vocabulary for representing reviews and ratings, as are often applied to products and services.
- The **Basic Geo (WGS84)** vocabulary (<http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/>) defines terms such as *lat* and *long* for describing geographically-located things.

In order to find other suitable vocabularies, as well as to analyze how widely deployed each vocabulary is, data providers can use the Vocabulary Catalog and Access Portal (<http://vocab.cc>) created as part of Planet Data deliverable D4.1 [46], as well as the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) project².

3.1.5 Are the URIs of proprietary vocabulary terms dereferenceable?

Data providers often define proprietary terms that are used in addition to terms from widely deployed vocabularies. In order to enable applications to automatically retrieve the definition of vocabulary terms from the Web, proprietary vocabularies should be made self-descriptive. Self-descriptiveness [44] means that an application which discovers some data on the Web that is represented using a previously unknown vocabulary should be able to find all meta-information that it requires to translate the data into a representation that it understands and can process. Therefore, the URIs identifying proprietary vocabulary terms should be made dereferenceable [8].

3.1.6 Do you map proprietary vocabulary terms to other vocabularies?

Proprietary vocabulary terms should be related to corresponding terms within other (widely used) vocabularies in order to enable applications to understand as much data as possible and to translate data into their target schemata. The Web Ontology Language (OWL), RDF Schema (RDFS), and the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) define RDF link types that can be used to represent such mappings. `owl:equivalentClass` and `owl:equivalentProperty` can be used to state that terms in different vocabularies are equivalent. If a looser mapping is desired, then `rdfs:subClassOf`, `rdfs:subPropertyOf`, `skos:broadMatch`, and `skos:narrowMatch` can be used.

²<http://labs.mondeca.com/dataset/lov>

3.1.7 Do you provide data set-level metadata?

In addition to making instance data self-descriptive, it is also desirable that data publishers provide metadata describing characteristic of complete data sets, for instance, the topic of a data set and more detailed statistics. Descriptions of a data set can include pointers to example resources, thereby aiding crawlers in discovering and indexing data. A data set can also include links to RDF data dumps, which can be downloaded and indexed separately, in case they wish to alleviate the load created by crawlers. Some of the recommended ways to describe a data set include *Semantic Sitemaps* [19] and *void* [2] descriptions.

3.1.8 Do you refer to additional access methods?

The primary way to publish Linked Data on the Web is to make the URIs that identity data items dereferenceable into RDF descriptions. In addition, various LOD data providers have chosen to provide two alternative means of access to their data via SPARQL endpoints or provide RDF dumps of the complete data set. If you do this, you should refer to the access points in your void description.

The *State of the LOD Cloud* document³ provides statistics about the extent to which deployed Linked Data sources meet the guidelines given above.

3.2 Best Practices for Linked Sensor Data

Linked Sensor data can be defined as “the application of Linked Data principles to sensor-based data” [56]. The usage of **Semantics** for sensor data provide better searching, **reasoning** through ontologies, and **integration** with other data sets (e.g. geographical). Examples of Sensor data and metadata modeling are presented in D1.1 [18].

We identified five major types of ingredients that are required to generate and consume Linked Sensor Data [17]:

1. A **core ontological model** describing sensors, sensor metadata, and sensor observations.
2. A set of additional **domain ontologies** in the area in which sensors are applied, to be aligned with the core ontology.
3. **Identifiers** for sensors, their observations and the features of interest that they observe.
4. **Sensor Web programming interfaces** (APIs) that make use of the HTTP protocol for dereferencing the corresponding previous URIs.
5. **Query processing engines** that support extended versions of SPARQL such as time and/or tuple windows.

In the following we describe a checklist for sharing Linked Sensor Data on the Web.

3.2.1 Do you use a recommended core ontological model?

The **SSN ontology** [16], proposed by the W3C Semantic Sensor Network incubator group⁴, is a domain-independent model that models sensor metadata and sensor observations. It can be considered the current standard to be followed.

3.2.2 Do you use domain ontologies?

- General purpose vocabularies. **Time**: the OWL-Time⁵ ontology is commonly used for representing time interval, instances, etc. **Location**: The Basic Geo WGS84 vocabulary⁶ and GeoVocab⁷ are widely used.

³<http://lod-cloud.net/state>

⁴<http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/>

⁵OWL-Time, <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/>

⁶<http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/>

⁷GeoVocab NeoGeo, <http://geovocab.org>

Quantities and Units of measurement: observation values usually come with a unit, for which there are available ontologies such as QUDT⁸ and QUDV⁹.

- Domain specific vocabularies. **Environmental:** phenomena, properties, materials and other concepts can be found in the SWEET ontologies¹⁰. **Meteorology:** AWS ontology for meteorological sensors¹¹. **Climate and Forecasts:** The CF ontology¹² is normally used to model climate and forecast information. **Coastal ontologies:** an example is the ontology network of the SemSorGrid4Env project¹³.

3.2.3 Do you have a URI scheme for your sensor data?

There is no agreement yet on a URI generation scheme for Linked Sensor Data, either sensor-centric [56] or observation-centric [33].

we recommend to use Patterned URIs¹⁴) by starting the URIs with the name of the class and followed by the identifiers. Then, at least the following URIs should be taken into account:

- **URIs for sensors** (and platforms, if it makes sense).
- **URIs for observations**
- **URIs for features of interest**
- **URIs for time periods**

3.2.4 Is your Sensor Web API ready?

- **Content negotiation** for dealing with identifiers described above. Like pubby¹⁵ for Linked (static) Data, but taking into account the dynamicity of Linked Sensor Data.
- Support for **push-based data** delivery protocols instead of the traditional pull-based ones
- They should be able to handle **RDF streams**, (i.e. timestamped triples [13]).
- Support for **aggregation of observations as links**, such as in [50].

See **SensorGrid4Env High-level API**¹⁶, **SpitFire project**¹⁷, and another proposal [4] for examples of Sensor Web APIs.

3.2.5 Does your Sensor Query Processor provide rich features?

- **SPARQL extensions.** The Sensor Query Processor should be able to handle some SPARQL extensions such as time and/or tuple windows.
- **Built-in function.** The Sensor Query Processor should be equipped with built-in functions related to time and interval.
- **Aggregation.** The Sensor Query Processor should be able to process queries that may contain aggregation of data.

⁸Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Data Types ontologies, <http://www.qudt.org/>

⁹Quantities, Units, Dimensions, Values OWL, http://www.omgwiki.org/OMGSystemML/doku.php?id=sysml-qudv:qudv_owl

¹⁰NASA Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology <http://sweet.jpl.nasa.gov/>

¹¹AWS Ontology, <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/meteo/aws>

¹²CF ontology, <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/cf/cf-property>

¹³SemSorGrid4Env ontologies, <http://www.sensorsgrid4env.eu/ontologies/>

¹⁴<http://patterns.dataincubator.org/book/patterned-uris.html>

¹⁵<http://www4.wiwiw.fu-berlin.de/pubby/>

¹⁶<http://www.sensorsgrid4env.eu/index.php/high-level-api>

¹⁷<http://spitfire-project.eu/>

- **Push and pull based.** The Sensor Query Processor should be able to support Push and Pull based data delivery.
- **Continuous queries.** The Sensor Query Processor should be able to execute of continuous, long-running and one-off queries.
- **Static and streaming.** The Sensor Query Processor should allow allow combining **static and streaming** query processing.

Examples of query languages for Sensor data include **SPARQL_{Stream}** [13], **C-SPARQL** [3], **CQELS** [42].

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this document we have presented a conceptual quality model and two example instantiations of this model for Linked Data and Sensor Data. We discussed data quality as a multi-dimensional, task-specific concept. Quality dimensions that have been proposed in literature were reviewed, resulting on the definition of a flexible quality model to support task-specific interpretations of quality. Our model is based on the usage of a variety of scoring functions applied to relevant indicators in order to create task-specific quality assessment metrics. Two concrete instantiations of the model are presented, for analyzing the quality of Linked Data and Linked Sensor Data on the Web. Best practices for high-quality data publishing on the Web are presented for both instantiations of our quality model. Throughout the next year, the consortium will further enhance the model and apply it to large scale data sets on the Web.

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